

To find varieties with higher yielding ability, B1 resistance, and acceptable grain quality, we have screened more than 6,000 varieties or lines since 1982. Most of the lines rated as resistant or moderately resistant to B1 in other parts of the world were found to be susceptible at Mbo Plain. (Climatic conditions there are highly conducive to B1.) A few entries, including ITA222 and CICA8, were found to be moderately resistant to both leaf and neck B1, with consistently higher yields than Tainan V, and superior grain quality (Table 1).

ITA222, a derivative of Mashir/IET1444 from the International Institute of Tropical Agriculture, has medium duration, medium height, good tillering ability, and an upright flag leaf. Its grains are long, with translucent kernels and flaky cooked texture (Table 2).

CICA8, a derivative of CICA4//IR665/Tetep from Centro Internacional de Agricultura Tropical, is shorter and has a longer growth duration than ITA222 and Tainan V. It has long, slender, translucent grains, which makes it competitive with imported rice in the ur-

Table 1. Yields of ITA222, CICA8, and Tainan V on-station and in farmers' fields at Mbo Plain, West Cameroon, 1985-88.

Variety	Grain yield ^a (t/ha)									
	On-station					On farm				
	1985	1986	1987	1988	Mean	1985	1986	1987	1988	Mean
ITA222	5.8	7.5	5.8	4.8	5.9	5.8	6.1	5.1	4.4	5.4
CICA 8	5.8	5.4	5.8	4.8	5.8	4.8	4.8	4.7	4.4	4.7
Tainan V (check)	8.4	4.1	8.9	4.2	5.6	8.7	8.5	8.8	8.0	8.4

^a Mean of 5 on-station and 5 on-farm trials each year.

Table 2. Characteristics of ITA222, CICA8, and Tainan V at Mbo Plain, Cameroon, 1985-88.

Variety	Plant height (cm)	Growth duration (d)	Reaction ^a to		
			Leaf blast	Neck blast	Grain type ^b
ITA222	95	104	MR	MS	L/S
CICA8	90	111	MR	MS	L/S
Tainan V (check)	108	95	S	MR	S/B

^a By the *Standard evaluation system for rice*. MR = moderately resistant, MS = moderately susceptible, S = susceptible. ^b L/S = long and slender, S/B = short and bold.

ban market. CICA8 was released in 1985 to replace Tainan V and is now widely grown at Mbo Plain.

ITA222 is in the pipeline for release, but like CICA8 and other promising va-

rieties, it shows increasing susceptibility to leaf and neck B1. Average B1 scores for CICA8 and ITA222 were 5.5 and 4.5, respectively, in 1988 compared with 3.0 in 1986. ■

Integrated germplasm improvement – rainfed

IET8717, a physiologically efficient rice variety for waterlogged areas of Assam

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IET8717 is a long-duration, high-yielding rice variety developed from TN1/Lua Ngu by the Directorate of Rice Research, Hyderabad, India. It is suitable for waterlogged conditions.

We tested IET8717 and other promising long-duration cultivars, and Manoharsali as check, under continuous waterlogged conditions (30-50 cm water depth) in the 1988 wet season (Jul-Nov). Entries were transplanted at 20- × 20-cm spacing. Forty kg N as urea was applied in three equal splits: 1 d before transplanting, 20 d after transplanting, and at panicle

initiation. The plants received a basal application of 8.8 kg P as single super-phosphate and 16.6 kg K as muriate of potash.

Table 1. Physical and physiological characteristics of IET8717 and Manoharsali. Titabar, Assam, India, 1988.

Character	IET8717	Manoharsali
Duration (d)	144	157
Height (cm)	116	133
Panicles/m ²	271	264
Grains/panicle	205	132
1000-grain wt (g)	19.05	19.08
Total dry matter at maturity (g/hill)	39.0	45.0
Grain yield (t/ha)	5.3	2.7
Harvest index	0.55	0.40
Postflowering photosynthetic contribution (%)	70.0	48.0
N content of leaves at flowering (%)	1.96	1.72
Total chlorophyll content at flowering (mg/g FW)	4.18	3.58
Proportion of high-density grain (%)	63.66	50.60

Duration of IET8717 was 144 d. It had 271 productive panicles/m², with 6.8% tiller mortality. Its grains were medium slender, with white kernels, and 1,000-grain weight of 19 g. Plant height was 115 cm with leaf area index of 6.6 at flowering, and harvest index of 0.55. High postflowering photosynthetic contribution (70%) results in higher panicle and grain numbers/m². Yield was 5.3 t/ha (Table 1).

IET8717 has shown high yielding ability and stability for 3 yr (Table 2). ■

Table 2. Yield of IET8717 and Manoharsali under continuous waterlogging. Titabar, Assam, India, 1987-89.

Year	IET8717		Manoharsali	
	Yield (t/ha)	Duration (d)	Yield (t/ha)	Duration (d)
1987	5.0	144	2.5	162
1988	4.8	144	2.7	163
1989	5.0	143	3.5	163